

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND MORPHOLOGY OF ACID MODIFIED CARBON NANOTUBE/DGEBA -BRIDGED POLYSILSESQUIOXANE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA)-bridged polyorganosiloxanes precursors have been prepared successfully by reacting diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A epoxy resin with (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane. Acid-modified and unmodified multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) were dispersed in the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A-bridged polyorganosiloxane precursors to prepare the carbon nanotube/ diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A-bridged polysilsesquioxane (CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ) nanocomposites.

SEM microphotographs demonstrate that acid-modified CNT exhibits better dispersion than unmodified CNT in DGBEA-PSSQ. The mechanical properties of nanocomposites depend strongly on the affinity between CNT and the polymer matrix. Adding multiwall carbon nanotubes markedly enhances the mechanical properties of nanocomposites. The mechanical properties of acid-modified CNT/DGBEA-PSSQ nanocomposites, except for tensile strength, are more favorable than those of unmodified CNT. Tensile strength depends on the length of the CNT. Acid modification reduced the length of CNT. Raman spectra also verified that acid modification destroyed the structure of CNT.

KEY WORDS: carbon nanotube, bridged polysilsesquioxane, nanocomposites, mechanical properties, morphology

INTRODUCTION

Since S. Ijima identified the structures of carbon nanotubes (CNT) in 1991[1], numerous investigations of CNTs have been undertaken because of their excellent electrical[2], mechanical[3], thermal and magnetic properties[4], low density, high strength, high toughness, high surface area, flexibility and chemical stability[5~7]. CNTs have great potential for use in polymer composites. Applications of carbon nanotube-modified polymers have been extensively examined[4]. The nanocomposites can be applied to aerospace and aircraft,

electrodes and bipolar plates of fuel cells, and other applications. Highly electrically conductive composites can be utilized as shielding materials for electromagnetic interference (EMI), radio frequency interference (RFI) and electrostatic discharge (ESD).

CNT/polymer composites, including matrices such as polyethylene (PE)[8], polypropylene (PP)[9], poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA)[10], poly(vinyl- carbazole) and polyamide[11], have been studied. Also, several works have been conducted to improve the characteristics of epoxy by incorporating CNT. [12]

Bridged polysilsesquioxanes are a family of hybrid organic-inorganic materials prepared by the sol-gel or modified sol-gel processing of monomers that contain a variable organic bridging group and two or more trifunctional silyl groups[13].

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Synthesis of DGEBA-PSSQ:

Epoxy (DGEBA type), Epon 828, was purchased Nan Ya Plastics Corp. Taiwan, and mixed with (3-aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES) which was obtained from Lancaster Synthesis Co., Morecambe: , England. Epoxy and APTES were mixed in the mole ratio 1:2; precursors of DGEBA-PSSQ will formed after 10 hour at room temperature (15°C) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Synthetic Method of DGEBA-PSSQ precursors from Epon 828 Epoxy.

Acidification of carbon nanotubes:

MWCNT was obtained from the Nanotech Port Company, Shenzhen, China. The diameters of the carbon nanotube were 40-60nm; their lengths were 0.5-40 μ m; their specific surface areas were 40-3000 m²/g. They were functionalized by refluxing with H₂SO₄-HNO₃ (3 : 2 by weight) for 24h, at 50°C [14].

Preparing CNT/ DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites:

Diglycidyl ether bisphenol A-bridged polyorganosiloxane precursors were mixed with carbon nanotubes. The sample was dispersed using an ultrasonic vibrator until there no phase separation was evident. Dibutyltindilaurate was used as a catalyst (obtained from Tokyo Chemical Industry Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan.), and was added to a mixture of the precursors DGEBA-PSSQ and CNT. The mixture was heated at 60°C for 72 hr, and then to 120°C at a rate of 10°C/hr. **Figure 2** presents the reaction of the precursors to yield DGEBA-PSSQ.

Figure 2 Cured DGEBA-PSSQ from the precursors

RESULTS AND DISSCUSSION

Morphology of CNT nanocomposites

Figures 3 displays SEM microphotographs of unmodified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites. Figure 3(a) presents SEM microphotographs of neat DGEBA-PSSQ. The polymer matrix is a homogeneous phase. Although unmodified CNTs in the DGEBA-PSSQ are aggregated, most are embedded in the DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites when the unmodified CNT content is 0.2wt% (Figs. 3(b,c)). A few of the clusters are in the unmodified CNT phase separately when the unmodified CNT content is 1.0wt%, suggesting that the unmodified CNT is not well dispersed in the composted materials, but embedded within the polymer matrix. Figures 3(d) and (e) show the SEM microphotographs of unmodified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ (1.0wt% unmodified CNT content). Figures 3(f) and (g) present SEM microphotographs of acid-modified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ. When CNTs were treated with acid, they were dispersed completely in the polymer matrix, the CNTs were all embedded inside the polymer matrix.

f.

Figure 3 SEM microphotograph of the DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposite, (a.) neat DGEBA-PSSQ (b) & (c) 0.2wt% unmodified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposite (b.50000 x c.4000x) (d)&(e) 1.0wt% unmodified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposite (d.50000 x e.2500x), (f) & (g) 1.0wt% acid-modified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposite (f.50000x g.10000x)

Mechanical properties

Tensile Properties

Figure 4 reveals that the tensile strength of cured DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites from 9.03MPa (the neat DGEBA-PSSQ) to 21.25MPa (0.8wt% unmodified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ), to 12.40MPa (0.8wt% acid-modified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ) and to 14.58MPa (1.0wt% acid-modified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ). Acid-modified CNT improves the tensile strength of the DGEBA-PSSQ less than does unmodified CNT. Acid treatment may shorten CNT, influencing the tensile strength of CNT.

Figure 4 Effect of CNT content on the Tensile Strength of DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites

Figure 5 indicates that the Young's modulus of cured DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites

increased from 0.56GPa (neat DGEBA-PSSQ) to 11.91GPa (0.8wt% unmodified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ), to 15.19GPa (0.8wt% acid-modified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ) and to 16.20GPa (1.0wt% acid-modified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ). Acid-modified CNT can improve the Young's Modulus of the DGEBA-PSSQ over that of unmodified CNT. The Young's modulus depends on the affinity of the filler toward the polymer matrix. Acid-modified CNT exhibits greater affinity toward the polymer matrix since the functional groups were formed.

Figure 5 Effect of CNT content on the Young's Modulus of DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites

Flexural Properties

Figure 6 demonstrates that the flexural strength of DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites increased from 40.62MPa (neat DGEBA-PSSQ) to 52.04MPa (0.8wt% unmodified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ) and to 68.41MPa (0.6wt% acid modified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ). Acid-modified CNT is associated with the DGEBA- PSSQ with a better flexural strength than does unmodified CNT.

Figure 6 Effect of CNT content on the Flexural strength of DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites

Figure 7 shows that the flexural modulus of DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites increased from 0.95GPa (neat DGEBA-PSSQ) to 17.07GPa (0.8wt% unmodified CNT/ DGEBA-PSSQ) and to 30.00GPa (0.8wt% acid modified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ). Acid-modified CNT is associated with a DGEBA-PSSQ with a better flexural modulus than is unmodified CNT.

Figure 7 Effect of CNT content on the Flexural Modulus of DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites

CONCLUSIONS

A novel multiwall carbon nanotube/DGEBA-bridged polysilsesquioxane nanocomposite was prepared successfully. The Raman spectra verified that acid treatment generated defects on the CNT.

SEM microphotographs indicate that unmodified CNT aggregated in the polymer matrix and acid-modified CNT was thoroughly dispersed in the polymer matrix.

The mechanical properties of CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ nanocomposites improved significantly with the CNT content. Acid-modified CNT has greater affinity than unmodified CNT toward the polymer matrix, so is associated with more improved mechanical properties. When the CNT content was 0.6wt%, the Young's modulus increased from 0.56GPa (neat resin) to 11.91GPa (unmodified CNT) and 15.19GPa (acid modified CNT). The flexural strength increased from 41MPa (neat resin) to 50MPa (unmodified CNT) and 68MPa (acid-modified CNT). The flexural modulus increased from 0.94GPa (neat resin) to 15.78GPa (unmodified CNT) and 15.44GPa (acid-modified CNT). Acid-modified CNT becomes shorter with more defects on its surface than unmodified CNT, so the associated improvement in tensile strength is less than that associated with unmodified CNT. For instance, when the CNT content was 0.6wt%, the tensile strength increased from 9MPa (neat resin) to 23MPa (unmodified CNT) and 11MPa (acid-modified CNT). The solid-state ^{13}C NMR CP/MAS demonstrates that acid-modified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ exhibits less molecular motion than neat DGEBA-PSSQ and unmodified CNT/DGEBA-PSSQ. Acid-modified CNT was attracted more strongly to DGEBA-PSSQ resin than was unmodified CNT. Hence, the associated improvements of Young's modulus, flexural strength and flexural modulus are therefore greater than those associated with unmodified CNT.

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